

SITE GPR	YEAR 2010	AREA B	SECTOR	ELEVATION Min: 63.1153 Max: 63.5249	STRATIGRAPHICAL UNIT 1170 <input type="checkbox"/> Natural <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Anthropic		
In cross-section? <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No		In elevation drawing? <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No		Photos: <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No #: 667-672	Photo Model: <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No #:		
DEFINITION ditch for rubble wall - M35				Covered by <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> SU: 1016	Fills <input type="checkbox"/> SU:	Filled by <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> SU: 1135	
HOW IS LAYER DISTINGUISHED? <input type="checkbox"/> Color <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Composition <input type="checkbox"/> Compaction			FORMATION PROCESS <input type="checkbox"/> Accumulation <input type="checkbox"/> Construction <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Cutting <input type="checkbox"/> Erosion <input type="checkbox"/> Collapse <input type="checkbox"/> Intentional deposition				
INCLUSIONS For each inclusion specify frequency: (f)requent, (m)edium, (r)are					SOIL/MATRIX		
Anthropic		Geological		Organic		clay ___% silt ___% sand ___%	
<input type="checkbox"/> Pottery <input type="checkbox"/> Tiles <input type="checkbox"/> Amphorae <input type="checkbox"/> Dolia <input type="checkbox"/> Mosaic tile(s) <input type="checkbox"/> Mortar <input type="checkbox"/> Coins <input type="checkbox"/> Metal (specify) <input type="checkbox"/> Collapse debris <input type="checkbox"/> Glass		<input type="checkbox"/> Nails <input type="checkbox"/> Marble <input type="checkbox"/> Quarried debris <input type="checkbox"/> Slag <input type="checkbox"/> Brick <input type="checkbox"/> Basalt slabs <input type="checkbox"/> Opus signinum <input type="checkbox"/> Painted plaster <input type="checkbox"/> Burnt Adobe <input type="checkbox"/> Other (specify)		<input type="checkbox"/> Tufo (specify) <input type="checkbox"/> Travertine <input type="checkbox"/> Other Limestone <input type="checkbox"/> Basalt <input type="checkbox"/> Clay <input type="checkbox"/> Sand <input type="checkbox"/> Silt <input type="checkbox"/> Pebbles (range) <input type="checkbox"/> Gravel (range)		<input type="checkbox"/> Charcoal <input type="checkbox"/> Ash <input type="checkbox"/> Animal bones <input type="checkbox"/> Human bones <input type="checkbox"/> Animal teeth <input type="checkbox"/> Human teeth <input type="checkbox"/> Shells <input type="checkbox"/> Other (specify)	<input type="checkbox"/> Granular <input type="checkbox"/> Layered <input type="checkbox"/> Cohesive Compaction <input type="checkbox"/> Hard <input type="checkbox"/> Compact <input type="checkbox"/> Friable <input type="checkbox"/> Loose <input type="checkbox"/> Soft
<input type="checkbox"/> Black <input type="checkbox"/> Brown <input type="checkbox"/> Gray <input type="checkbox"/> Light Brown <input type="checkbox"/> Light Gray <input type="checkbox"/> White <input type="checkbox"/> Yellow <input type="checkbox"/> Red <input type="checkbox"/> Light Yellow <input type="checkbox"/> Other (specify)							
UNIT LIMITS (also indicate on overlay)							
Northern Limit		<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Original <input type="checkbox"/> Not Original <input type="checkbox"/> Excavation Limit		Depth: <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Original <input type="checkbox"/> Not Original			
Southern Limit		<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Original <input type="checkbox"/> Not Original <input type="checkbox"/> Excavation Limit					
Western Limit		<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Original <input type="checkbox"/> Not Original <input type="checkbox"/> Excavation Limit					
Eastern Limit		<input type="checkbox"/> Original <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Not Original <input type="checkbox"/> Excavation Limit		cut by 1152			
STRATIGRAPHICAL SEQUENCE							
Is equal to:			Is bound to (only for masonry):				
Is abutted by:			Abuts:				
Is covered by: 1016			Covers:				
Is cut by: 1152			Cuts: 1169, 1165				
Is filled by: 1135			Fills:				
OBSERVATIONS soil of cut on S side removed during excavation of 1016 and 1165							
DESCRIPTION Position within sector: W edge of excavated area of Area B Shape: rectangular oriented W-E							
For layers complete this section:							
Surface (slope direction; visible inclusions):							
Observations about inclusions (Clusters? Deposition slope):							
Observations about thickness (Increases? Decreases?):							
Nature of the interface with layer below: <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> sharp <input type="checkbox"/> diffuse <input type="checkbox"/> commingled <input type="checkbox"/> other (specify)							
For cuts complete this section:			Sketch for layers and/or cuts (indicate North):				
Cut edges: <input type="checkbox"/> rounded <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> straight							
Cut sides: <input type="checkbox"/> straight <input type="checkbox"/> concave <input type="checkbox"/> convex <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> sloping							
Cut bottom: <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> flat <input type="checkbox"/> concave <input type="checkbox"/> irregular							
How is cut top edge? <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> sharp <input type="checkbox"/> rounded							
How is cut bottom edge? <input type="checkbox"/> sharp <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> rounded							
Observations: top edge of cut on S side removed through exposure of 1135 wall			<div style="text-align: right;"> unexcavated (vet) soil </div>				

For structural remains complete this section

Alignment:

Building Technique: Adobe/Mud-brick Ashlar (blocks) irregular (unworked) stone Concrete Other (specify)

Binding Agent: None Clay Mortar (if so, specify composition, color, compaction)

Concrete inclusions:

Material: Tufo Basalt Travertine Tiles Other (specify)

Size: Small (range) _____ Medium (range) _____ Large (range) _____ Representative size: e.g. 2 x 1 x 2 cmz

Wall Facing:

Opus quadratum Opus incertum Opus reticulatum Petit appareil Opus testaceum Opus mixtum Opus vittatum Other (specify)

Complete this section for foundations Faced foundation Wooden shuttering No shuttering

floor/revetment type

Floor type: Beaten Earth Opus signinum Opus scutulatum Opus Sectile Mosaic Opus spicatum Other (specify)

Wall finishing: Stucco Opus signinum Plaster Painted Plaster Other (specify)

Approx. length, width, height of structural remains:

Description:

Sketch (if applicable, indicate North)

INTERPRETATION

disc which was dug for the construction of wall 1135.

SOIL SAMPLING: Yes No

Total volume of layer (buckets):

Sample quantity (buckets):

Sample fraction (%):

NON SOIL SAMPLES: Yes No

If yes, specify (e.g. charcoal, mortar etc.):

Size:

SIEVING: Yes No

Total volume of layer (buckets):

Sample quantity (buckets):

Sample fraction (%):

STRATIGRAPHICAL RELIABILITY

Good Fair Poor

Filled-out by LMB

on 19.07.2010

Revised by CMH

on 19.07.2010

PDFd by

on

Entered by

on